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**Upholding the School Policies on Alternative Delivery Modes
and Basic Education Learning Continuity for Senior High**

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Silvestre C. Villarín

Tuburan National High School, Schools Division of Cebu Province, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6668-1334>

Beverly Jean D. Uy

Tuburan National High School, Schools Division of Cebu Province, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-5444>

Arline R. Gungob

Tuburan National High School, Schools Division of Cebu Province, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6163-1372>

Servando B. Uy III

Cebu Technological University- Tuburan Campus, Tuburan, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9342-2735>

Pinky Grace M. Labastida

Duangan Elementary School, Schools Division of Cebu Province, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0757-2281>

Moonyeen S. Allego

Tuburan Central Elementary School, Schools Division of Cebu Province, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6911-8261>

Abstract

This research determined the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality policy and basic education learning continuity plan in identified subjects of Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) among Grade 12 Senior High School students in Tuburan National High School, DepEd Tuburan, during the academic year 2021- 2022, as basis for an action plan. This research utilized the descriptive-survey method employing the modified adopted questionnaires in gathering data which were treated using simple percentage, the weighted mean, and the t-test. These findings on the presented data, the following are herein provided: The student's status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality and learning continuity plan has an average weighted mean of 4.12 interpreted as Agree, wherein the policy dimensions that got the lowest mean is the alternative learning modality on modules distribution with 3.90 interpreted as Agree. And the teacher's perception has an average weighted mean of 4.20 interpreted as Agree, where the policy dimensions that got the lowest mean of 3.83 interpreted as Agree is the alternative learning modality on retrieval of modules. There is significant difference between the students and teachers' perception on the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality and a significant similarity between the students' and teachers' perception with regards to the student's performance of basic education learning continuity plan. Thereupon, an action plan should be developed and implemented using school policies on alternative delivery modality and basic education learning continuity plan.

Keywords: Administration and supervision, alternative delivery modes, basic education learning continuity, descriptive-survey method, school policies, Tuburan Cebu, Philippines

Introduction

A policy is typically a plan with a set of guidelines created for simple governance inside an organization. Institutions must have implementable policies because they serve as a connecting thread between the administration of the school, the faculty, the students, the parents, and the legal system. Without a policy, an institution lacks control over its operations.

One of the major ways that governments influence children's lives is through education policy. As a result, schools and education policy seem to be a crucial area of concern for governments and politicians aiming to maximize subjective well-being when instinctual well-being is gaining a lot of policy attention.

In England, educational policy has changed consistently and steadily throughout the past 30 years, with little consideration for how these changes may affect children's cognitive development. Experts and observers have

expressed concern about these developments and how they will affect children's lives due to the nature and scope of these changes. The trajectory of policy hasn't changed much, if at all, despite this. To optimize educational achievement and guarantee better lives for children as they grow older, proponents of the modifications have claimed that they are both essential and desirable.

The Philippines has a strong and diverse educational system, with the government, backed by the private sector, offering a wide spectrum of education from early years up to college and university throughout the archipelago. The distribution of basic education is under the direction of the Department of Education (DepEd). The private neighborhood has kindergartens, international schools, and religious schools. The Philippines has finally launched its most innovative reform of the educational system in decades, the K-12 reform program, four years after the Expanded Basic Education Act (EBEA, also known as the K-12 law) was put into effect.

One of the most crucial factors that affects a person's and a country's progress is education. The new coronavirus outbreak, also known as COVID-19, had a significant impact on many people's lives. The necessity to maintain tight social or physical distance to prevent or limit the spread of COVID-19 presently has the largest impact on the disease. COVID-19 is affecting all facets of life, including education, in addition to contributing to difficulties with global health. For DepEd, this means canceling classes and other educational activities for the remaining weeks of SY 2019–2020, SY 2020–21, and SY 2021–2022. Notwithstanding the threat and uncertainty posed by the coronavirus, schools must find a method to continue teaching while setting the seal on the health, safety, and security of all learners, teachers, and personnel of the department - The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the Time of COVID-19.

In the event of the global pandemic, distance learning as an educational situation in which a teacher and his/her students are not in the same physical environment. The teaching career necessitates not only the ability to cope with change but also the ability to teach others how to prepare for and cope with the change. To achieve qualities like this, teachers must engage in ongoing professional growth, but perhaps more importantly, they must be aware and prepared for the involuntarily triggered by a coronavirus outbreak, we switched to distance learning. DepEd administered policies on the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) during the period of COVID 19. By stopping the spread of COVID-19, this may contribute to the preservation of the health, welfare, and safety of students, teachers, and other staff members. Achieved learning continuity through K–12 schedule modifications, the pairing of learning resources, the use of many learning delivery modalities, the provision of matching training for teachers and school administrators, and the proper orientation of parents or guardians of learners.

To meet the New Normal, the distinct areas of government, including education, were straightened. The process had undergone many changes in a short period and had made significant progress in maintaining its purpose. Despite being the center of the government, education, and economy, Metro Manila was unprepared for it. Lack of technology and a poor internet connection were only two of the issues that prevented it from fulfilling its mandate to provide students with a high quality education. To assure safety among the various stakeholders, the DepEd created the BE LCP, which included various learning modalities. The Central Office gave the field offices and schools around the nation the policy guidance to start their operations before the official start of classes in October 2020.

Literature Review

The study is premised on the following theories about the Educational Learning Objectives of Bloom's Taxonomy, Five Educational Learning Theories of Paul Stevens- Fulbrook and anchored on DepEd Order No. 012, series of 2020 known as "Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in light of the Covid-19 Public Health Emergency" and DepEd Order No. 54, series of 2020 known as "Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Alternative Delivery Modes".

Promoting students' successful learning and well-being depends on having effective school discipline policies and practices. They promote advancement toward long-term learning and behavioral goals while preserving the integrity of the educational environment, assuring the protection and dignity of all students and staff, and strengthening students' behavioral abilities by addressing the causes of their misbehaviors. Effective school discipline is hampered by several factors, including the widespread use of punitive measures and inconsistent, discriminatory policies and procedures that frequently disproportionately affect minorities and students with disabilities. The three learning domains of cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor are included in educational learning objectives. Learning can take place within each domain at a variety of levels, from simple to complex. The cognitive domain focuses on mental abilities including analytical reasoning, problem-solving, and producing cognitive content. The attitudes, values, interests, and appreciation of learners are the core topics of the affective domain. The ability of learners to physically complete tasks, perform movements, and master abilities falls within the psychomotor domain. The domains that make up Bloom's Taxonomy Model are as follows (Armstrong, 2016). According to Fulbrook (2019), who has developed a set of educational theories, both aspiring and practicing teachers should receive an education to prepare them for the day-to-day challenges of teaching. Knowledge of

alternative learning methods is a crucial component of this education. The preparation for assisting learners in the classroom can benefit teachers. Understanding diverse types of learning allows teachers to adapt their teaching methods in the classroom, which may assist all students to succeed in their academic endeavors.

The DepEd Order No. 012 has been released by the Department of Education. The Basic Education Learning Continuity Strategy for the Academic Year 2020–2021 is Adopted considering the Covid-19 Public Health Emergency in 2020. Considering the scenarios predicted by the Department of Health (DOH) and the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases within the Philippines (IATF), as well as other reliable sources, and balancing them with DepEd's risk assessments, BE-LCP facilitates the safe return of teaching and non-teaching personnel and students to workplaces and schools. Considering the risks, difficulties, and uncertainty posed by COVID-19, DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones has directed that all students, instructors, and department employees must be assured of their health, safety, and welfare, while also finding ways or learning to continue. This memorandum enables students to reinforce their learning competency.

Petrie (2020), When schools are shuttered to deal with the pandemic around the world, children, parents, and teachers have experienced the unanticipated ripple effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Education systems are trying to carry on providing high-quality education for everyone during these trying times while governments, frontline staff, and health officials try to contain the spread. Numerous students living at home or in communal spaces are suffering from psychological and emotional pain and are unable to communicate effectively. We haven't yet investigated the most basic methods of internet homeschooling. While the vulnerable students fail exams and internal exams due to fewer student-teacher interactions and a lack of teacher consultation, the naturally motivated students are mostly unaffected by this because they receive little monitoring and direction when facing difficulties in learning and understanding (Sintema, 2020).

DepEd Child Protection Policy (2012), all schools or educational institutions shall impose policies or regulations that may improve the discipline and behavior of the learners, but it mustn't harm the learners physically, verbally, and emotionally; make sure that all pupils, school personnel, parents, guardians or custodians, and visitors must remember of the policy; also make sure the participatory and other rights of learners are respected and upheld all told matters and procedures affecting their welfare. There are challenges when there is a group of weak learners. Some academically strong students from underprivileged families are unable to access and cannot afford online schooling. For the lessons held during the two years, the student's level of educational performance will likely decline.

Methodology

Research design

This study employed the descriptive-survey method of research design in presenting and discussing the profile, status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality and learning continuity plan, significant relationship between the teachers and students on the status of the implementation of alternative delivery modes and the student's performance of basic education learning continuity plan. The data gathered were presented, analyzed, and interpreted which were used as the basis for the presentation of findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Respondents of the study

This study chose the Senior High School of Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Students and Senior High School Teachers from Tuburan National High School, DepEd Cebu Province, District of Tuburan I. The sampling size was determined using Slovin's Formula and the respondents of the study were selected using a stratified random sampling method for students and complete enumeration of all senior high school teachers was also considered in the study. There were 50 students enrolled per section for a total of 284 and 20 senior high school teachers will be selected as respondents.

Table 1 Distribution of the Respondents.

Respondents	Strand	Students Enrolled / Number of Teachers	f	%
Students	HUMSS	284	150	100
Teachers		20	20	100
Total		304	170	100

Research instrument

The research instruments used in the study were composed of three sections which assessed the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes and the student's performance of the basic education learning continuity plan. The questionnaire was divided into three sections (I-III); Section I was for gathering data on respondents' personal information; Section II was made up of questions that elicited responses

from respondents about students' performance with response options: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Partially Agree (PA), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD); and Section III will concentrate on issues and concerns encountered by respondents concerning school policies.

Data-Gathering Procedure

To conduct the study, a Transmittal Letter was sent to the relevant authorities. Following the approval, a letter asking the principal's permission to conduct the study at Tuburan National High School was delivered. Following receiving permission, the researcher used Google Forms to send the questionnaire to the respondents. The techniques for collecting data and the goal of the study were properly explained during the consent processes for the respondents' parents and for the respondents themselves. Respondents were given the option to either participate in the study or not; they were not coerced into doing so.

Scoring Procedure

This study employed the following procedures:

For the respondents' status on the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality and learning continuity plan, the weighted mean for each competency as well as the overall weighted mean of the five competencies was interpreted using the Likert five-point scale of ratings.

Findings and Discussion

The following are the results of the gathered data in determining the status of the implementation of the school policies of the students and teachers along alternative learning modality in terms of module distribution, swapping of modules, retrieval of modules, and safety health protocols and learning continuity plan in terms of written works, performance tasks and assessment. The last part discussed the issues and concerns met by the respondent groups.

Alternative Learning Modality

This section describes the status of the implementation of the school policies as perceived by the students and teachers.

Modules Distribution

Based on the data tabulated, it revealed that out of five (5) modules distribution policy dimensions Strongly Agree was the Modules are distributed on time with a weighted mean of 4.50. Both the students and the teachers perceived that this policy works well in acquiring the policy and achieving proficiency. Enhancing students' interactions with teachers will benefit both their academic performance and long-term success. The school must maintain policies for the students they entail to promote good values and to make them manage in making choices and decisions in life.

As reflected in Table 2 on the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality modules distribution policy dimensions of the students and teachers have an average weighted mean of 4.03 which is rated Agree.

According to DepEd Order No.018 (2020), school officials and teachers shall impose and establish the guidelines that will enable the Department of Education to provide learning resources in the implementation of the BE-LCP on alternative learning modality.

Table 2 reflects the modules' distribution policy dimensions.

Modules Distribution	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Modules are distributed on time.	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.50	Strongly Agree
2. Modules are complete.	4.14	Agree	3.85	Agree
3. Modules are in good condition.	3.43	Agree	4.0	Agree
4. Modules are distributed online.	3.43	Agree	4.0	Agree
5. Modules are distributed physically.	4.01	Agree	4.45	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.90	Agree	4.16	Agree

* $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Empirical studies showed mixed results with regards to the status on the implementation of school policy. Studies have found that the participation of students on the implementation of school policy may have both positive and negative impacts on their academic performance. The learner is responsible for accomplishing the activities

contained in the modules in their own personal and unique manner of learning and can completely complete the task on each module. Ultimately, DepEd released the policy guidelines to "unify the understanding of the K to 12 and to improve the implementation of each component, project, and activity under it," with a specific focus on "explaining the K to 12 curriculum and the programs for each stage, describing the learner and their ability at each key stage and showing the curriculum, mandate, and appraisal for each key stage; to establish the components required to ensure constructive implementation (Briones, 2019).

Swapping of Modules

Based on the data tabulated, it revealed that out of five (5) swapping of modules policy dimensions, most items rated agree by the students and teachers. The responses of the students obtained an average mean of 3.97 interpreted as Agree and the same holds with the teacher's perception with a weighted average of 3.90.

Table 3 presents the swapping of modules' policy dimensions.

Swapping of Modules	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Swapping of modules is required.	4.09	Agree	3.95	Agree
2. The swapping of modules is smooth.	3.78	Agree	3.40	Partially Agree
3. Swapping of modules is time-bound.	3.87	Agree	3.85	Agree
4. Students exchange their modules within the nearest purok.	4.06	Agree	4.40	Strongly Agree
5. Students exchange their modules with their partners.	4.06	Agree	3.90	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.97	Agree	3.90	Agree

* $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)

As reflected in Table 3 the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality swapping of modules policy dimensions of the students and teachers has an average weighted mean of 3.94 which is rated Agree.

The strategy implementation includes using a variety of learning delivery methods because COVID-19 will likely last for at least a year, if not longer before most people are fully immunized. The Department of Education cannot afford to keep the schools closed for so long. For the students, it has a big long-term effect.

Incredible societal and human costs are incurred as a result. Research has demonstrated that it can set learners back several years, even into adulthood, by keeping schools open but secure. Nothing, not even the pandemic, can obstruct our students' teachings and formations. The result implies that the status of the implementation of the school policy has become an integral part of the student's life; it is now seen as a learning platform that could be utilized to enhance student participation, engagement, and performance. The Policy might help with its efficient implementation and development. An educator must have a conceptual understanding of the self-learning strategy as well as the schedule of self-learning modules and materials for this learning process to be effective.

Reduced learning time during the pandemic is likely to have interfered with students' learning and stunted their overall development. We will need to invent for this time once the pandemic permits it by increasing both the amount and quality of learning time through proffer schedules, summer enrichment, and after-school activities, more individualized mandate, and staffing strategies that reduce class sizes and staff schools with sufficient and highly qualified educators (Garcia & Weiss, 2020).

Retrieval of Modules

Based on the data tabulated it revealed that out of five (5) retrieval of modules policy dimensions, four (4) items were rated agree by the student and teacher respondents. The responses of the students obtained an average weighted mean of 4.05 interpreted as Agree and the same holds with the teachers' perception with an average weighted mean of 3.84.

Table 4 presents the retrieval of modules' policy dimensions.

Retrieval of Modules	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Retrieval of modules is on time.	4.23	Strongly Agree	4.00	Agree
2. Retrieval of modules is complete.	4.21	Strongly Agree	3.50	Agree
3. Retrieval of modules is in good condition.	4.15	Agree	3.65	Agree
4. Retrieval of modules answer sheets submitted online.	3.32	Partially Agree	3.65	Agree
5. Retrieval of modules answer sheets submitted physically.	4.35	Strongly Agree	4.40	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.05	Agree	3.84	Agree

** $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)*

As reflected in Table 4 the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality retrieval of modules policy dimensions of the students and teachers have an average weighted mean of 3.95 which is rated Agree.

The results imply that students have satisfactorily followed the implemented policy dimensions. Teachers encountered some problems in terms of collecting the modules because some students wouldn't be able to pass their modules and answer sheets on time. It can cause the teachers to make the grades late.

The modules are designed to guide the learners in understanding the concepts and learning the skills. However, the modules may not be enough to master the lessons, thus, as provided in the Policy Memorandum DM-CI-2020-000 issued by the Office of the Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction, teachers shall be trusted and tasked to develop and prepare activity sheets. This is supplementing the modules for the intent of enhancement and must be anchored on Most Essential Learning Competencies (Department of Education, 2020).

Safety Health Protocols

Based on the data tabulated, it revealed that out of five (5) safety health protocols policy dimensions, almost were rated strongly agree by the student and teacher respondents. The responses of the students obtained an average weighted mean of 4.32 interpreted as Strongly Agree and the same holds with the teachers' perception with an average weighted mean of 4.57.

As reflected in Table 5 the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality safety health protocols policy dimensions of the students and teachers has an average weighted mean of 4.45 which is rated Strongly Agree.

Table 5 reveals the safety health protocols policy dimensions.

Safety Health Protocols	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Check body temperature is required.	4.52	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
2. Face Covering is observed.	4.43	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
3. Goggles and Face Shields are needed.	3.77	Agree	4.25	Strongly Agree
4. Hand Washing is essential.	4.48	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
5. Physical Distancing is requisite.	4.42	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.32	Strongly Agree	4.57	Strongly Agree

** $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)*

The findings reveal that 100 percent of the respondents are very satisfactory with observing health protocols. The policy is an essential part of the all-encompassing efforts to maintain the safety of students and faculty while also providing learning and social opportunities to keep students interested. To achieve the institutional goal, everyone must take personal responsibility and commit to following health regulations.

Summary of the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality

Table 6 displays the summary of the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality.

Factors	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Modules Distribution	3.90	Agree	4.16	Agree
2. Swapping of Modules	3.97	Agree	3.90	Agree
3. Retrieval of Modules	4.05	Agree	3.84	Agree
4. Safety Health Protocols	4.32	Strongly Agree	4.57	Strongly Agree
Factor Average Mean	4.06	Agree	4.12	Agree

* $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)

This deals with the summary of the status on the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality as rated by the students and teachers on the policy dimensions as to modules distribution, swapping of modules, retrieval of modules, and safety health protocols.

As reflected in Table 6, summing all the ratings, The student's status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative learning modality has an average weighted mean of 4.06 interpreted as Agree, wherein the policy dimensions that got the lowest mean is the alternative learning modality on modules distribution with 3.90 interpreted as Agree. The teacher's perception has an average weighted mean of 4.12 interpreted as Agree, where the policy dimensions that got the lowest mean of 3.84 interpreted as Agree is the alternative learning modality on retrieval of modules.

It is crucial to integrate cognitive theory into teacher training to increase the appeal of cognition in the education of all students. They can act as both direct and indirect supports for learning, the advancement of teachers' use of cognition and critical thinking instruction, learning, and assessment, as well as a means of relieving stress associated with school and validating creative work. (P. Armstrong, 2016).

Learning Continuity Plan

This section describes the status on the implementation of the school policies as perceived by the students and teachers.

Written Works

Table 7 shows the written works policy dimensions.

Written Works	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. The answer to the modules shall be written in an intermediate pad.	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.70	Strongly Agree
2. Reflection and reaction papers are required.	4.35	Strongly Agree	4.55	Strongly Agree
3. Journals and essays are submitted on time.	4.16	Agree	3.85	Agree
4. Written works are submitted online.	3.77	Agree	3.75	Agree
5. Written works are submitted physically.	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.5	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.26	Strongly Agree	4.27	Strongly Agree

* $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Based on the data tabulated, it revealed that out of five (5) written works policy dimensions, almost were rated strongly agree by the student and teacher respondents. The responses of the students obtained an average weighted mean of 4.26 interpreted as Strongly Agree and the same holds with the teachers' perception with an average weighted mean of 4.27.

As reflected in Table 7 the status of the implementation of the school policies on learning continuity plan on the written works policy dimensions of the students and teachers has an average weighted mean of 4.27 which is rated Strongly Agree.

The results show that students at this level have mastered the necessary information, abilities, and key concepts with the help of their teachers and can communicate these concepts through genuine written works. This is a good remark and the need to fully enhance the policy and to promote the welfare of the students.

The DepEd policy on modular learning presents difficulties for teachers and students when conducting assessments in the relevant subjects, such as limitations on providing immediate feedback and the requirement to take different contexts into account when planning, carrying out, and grading written assignments. In this modern era, schools must implement assessment and grading procedures that may most intelligently promote student progress and respond to a variety of circumstances (Briones, 2019).

Performance Tasks

Table 8 discloses the learning continuity plan on the performance tasks policy dimensions.

Performance Tasks	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Projects are made and are submitted on time.	4.18	Agree	3.85	Agree
2. Multimedia presentations are created.	3.65	Agree	3.75	Agree
3. Essay writing activities are available in the modules.	4.16	Agree	4.55	Strongly Agree
4. Skills demonstration (Singing, playing instruments, drawing, and other demonstration skills) are properly documented.	3.81	Agree	3.75	Agree
5. Designing and implementation of the action plans are parts of the module's investigatory projects.	3.99	Agree	4.25	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.96	Agree	4.03	Agree

** $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)*

Based on the data tabulated, it revealed that out of five (5) performance tasks policy dimensions, almost were agreed by the student and teacher respondents. The responses from the learners received an average weighted mean of 3.96, which was interpreted as "Agree," while the teachers' perspective received an average weighted mean of 4.03 as well.

As reflected in Table 8 the performance tasks policy dimensions of the students and teachers have an average weighted mean of 4.00 which is rated Agree.

This signifies that the students agree with the implementation of the policy during the crisis and improve their activities in enhancing their skills and abilities in different performance tasks. Policy on the Department of Education performance tasks that were used to evaluate the performance standards and content that represent the knowledge, skills, and abilities that students should possess.

According to cognitive learning theory, learners are affected since knowing how they think can help them learn. Both passive and active participation by individuals in the growth process is possible. Although people actively analyze the information they are given, they also play a passive role in what is being modeled and witnessed. Both internal and external factors have the potential to have an impact on learners. Humans are proactive, self-organizing, self-reflective, and self-regulating (Susman, 2021).

Assessment

Based on the data tabulated, it revealed that out of five (5) assessment policy dimensions, almost were rated strongly agree by the student and teacher respondents. The responses of the students obtained an average weighted mean of 4.36 interpreted as Strongly Agree and the same holds with the teachers' perception with an average weighted mean of 4.62.

Table 9 presents the assessment policy dimensions.

Assessment	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Assessments are conducted regularly.	4.38	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
2. Online assessments are done through the google forms web-based platform.	4.35	Strongly Agree	4.70	Strongly Agree
3. A hard copy of the assessments is provided.	4.24	Strongly Agree	4.45	Strongly Agree
4. Summative assessment tools are available in the modules.	4.33	Strongly Agree	4.70	Strongly Agree
5. The Assessment aims to monitor and evaluate the holistic and authentic attainment of Most Essential Learning Competencies.	4.51	Strongly Agree	4.65	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.36	Strongly Agree	4.62	Strongly Agree

* $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)

As reflected in Table 9, the assessment policy dimensions of the students and teachers has an average weighted mean of 4.49 which is rated Strongly Agree.

The findings show that students have satisfactorily followed the policy dimensions that have been put into practice and have acquired the core information, abilities, and understanding necessary to become independent learners who can do their study and work on assessments.

According to DepEd, assessments should be created to inform, develop, and support classroom procedures and foster learning outcomes. It is employed to keep track of how well students are doing in terms of meeting learning standards and developing 21st-century abilities, to promote self-reflection and personal responsibility among students, and to provide the foundation for portraying student performance.

Summary of the Status of the Implementation of the School Policies on Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan
This deals with the summary of the status on the implementation of the school policies on basic education learning continuity plan as rated by the students and teachers on the policy dimensions as to written works, performance tasks, and assessment.

Table 10 displays the summary of the status of the implementation of the school policies on the basic education learning continuity plan.

Factors	Students (150)		Teachers (20)	
	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Written Works	4.26	Strongly Agree	4.27	Strongly Agree
2. Performance Tasks	3.96	Agree	4.03	Agree
3. Assessment	4.36	Strongly Agree	4.62	Strongly Agree
Factor Average Mean	4.19	Agree	4.31	Strongly Agree

* $\bar{x}$ - Mean; 4.21 - 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41 - 4.20 Agree (A); 2.61 - 3.40 Partially Agree (PA); 1.81 - 2.60 Disagree (D); 1.00 - 1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)

As reflected in Table 10, summing all the ratings, The student's status of the implementation of the school policies on basic education learning continuity plan has an average weighted mean of 4.19 interpreted as Agree, wherein the policy dimensions that got the lowest mean is the basic education learning continuity plan on performance tasks with 3.96 interpreted as Agree. The teacher's perception has an average weighted mean of 4.31 interpreted as Strongly Agree, where the policy dimensions that got the lowest mean of 4.03 interpreted as Agree is the basic education learning continuity plan on performance. This implies that students at this time have learned essential

counsel, capacity, and core apprehension and can transfer this understanding through performance tasks with little help from their parents, teachers, or peers.

Sanni (2017), asserts that factors influencing the quality of education and students' academic success across a range of subjects include their study habits. It is unrealistic to expect students to acquire everything they need to know about a subject from their lecturers during a modular course; instead, students' study habits are the result of a combination of in-class and outside-of-class learning. It is impossible to overstate the importance of providing students with effective guidance services to attain high academic success. The requirement for better study habits that would enhance good academic achievement should be stressed to the students. It was noted that learners who had developed and organized study habits did better on assessments. Continued advising parents, stakeholders, and teachers should provide learning materials and a conducive environment for effective learning (Okon, 2017).

Test of significant relationship between the teachers and students on the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes and the student's performance of basic education learning continuity plan. This part deals with the test of a significant relationship between the relationship of the respondent groups who were the students and the teachers on the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes and the student's performance of the basic education learning continuity plan.

Table 11 reflects the data on the significant relationship between the Teachers and Students on the Status of the Implementation of the School Policies on Alternative Delivery Modes.

Relationship	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t-Value	p-Value	Interpretation	Decision
Students' Perception Mean	4.11	0.357	-0.112	0.912	not significant	Accept H ₀
Teachers' Perception Mean	4.10	0.434				

As reflected in Table 20, from the table analysis, the perception of the respondents on the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes. Students had a weighted mean of 4.11 with a standard deviation of 0.357; teachers' perceptions had a weighted mean of 4.10 with a standard deviation of 0.434. It was found that the p-value was 0.912 and the computed t-value was -0.112. Since the p-value was higher than the 0.05 level and the t-value was lower than the critical value of the t-table (1.7291). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, it can be stated that there was no significant relationship between the students and teachers on the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes. As presented in the table, the weighted mean results of the students and teachers, including the computed t-value clearly show and verify the veracity of the concluded hypothesis. This reveals that the students and teachers have different perceptions of the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes. This significantly tells us that the school is the resemble of the school policy and the gateway in providing a conducive learning environment.

A similar study by Coeckelbergh (2020) that the relationship between teachers' empathy and opinions of their school's policy, teachers' ability to change the policy of their school may be constrained by their failure to correctly read and react to student behavior.

The study evidenced that student factors like gender have a big impact on academic success, but there are no studies that show how well male and female learners perform differently when it comes to the effectiveness of modular learning. The effectiveness of modular distance learning is heavily reliant on parental experience and student applications (Manire, 2021).

Table 12 indicates the data on which the significant relationship between the Teachers and Students in the student's performance of basic education learning continuity plan is being presented.

Relationship	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t-Value	p-Value	Interpretation	Decision
Students' Perception Mean	4.08	0.393	2.284	0.021	Significant	Reject H0
Teachers' Perception Mean	4.29	0.387				

As reflected in Table 12, from the table analysis, the perception of the respondents in the student's performance of basic education learning continuity plan. Students had a weighted mean of 4.08 with a standard deviation of 0.393; teachers' perceptions had a weighted mean of 4.29 with a standard deviation of 0.387. It was found that the p-value was .021 and the t-value was 2.284.

Since the p-value was lower than 0.05 level and the t-value was higher than the critical value of t table (1.7291). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, it can be stated that there was a significant relationship between the students and teachers in the student's performance of basic education learning continuity plan. As presented in the table, the weighted mean results of the students and teachers, including the computed t-value clearly show and verify the veracity of the concluded hypothesis. This reveals that the students and teachers have the same perception of the student's performance of the basic education learning continuity plan. This significantly shows that school policies are so are intended to help students reliably, fairly, and safely as per the regulatory standard. A similar study by Okon (2017) demonstrated that students' academic performance was highly influenced by the training, experience, and teacher-to-student ratio of their teachers. The results can be utilized to inform planners about the necessity of trained instructors to support efficient teaching and learning. It's a common belief that educational standards can never rise above the caliber of the teachers. Through classroom management and academic motivation, the trust between students and teachers made a distinctive contribution to students' performance.

For schools to maintain some level of accountability in the eyes of both internal and external stakeholders, policies must be in place. Schools are dedicated to upholding the law of the land (Clair, A., 2014).

Conclusion

As revealed in the study, implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes and learning continuity plans will improve the learning competency and performance of the students. Based on the findings; respondents agree as to the status of the implementation of the school policies on alternative delivery modes policy dimensions and learning continuity plan policy dimensions. Henceforth, there is a need to improve the policy and fully understand the implementation of the proficiency level of the students in making them ready through adapting a developed action plan that would help the students adopt the implementation requirements. Therefore, the light of the findings and conclusion of the study, it is recommended to implement an action plan and interaction tasks, especially in the lowest policy dimension to escalate their skills, abilities, and proficiency to ensure the maximum development of their capacity vis-à-vis the existing school policies on Alternative Learning Modality and Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan.

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